

Applications and developments of BMF analytics/MT over time

AISDL Team

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“– Great Master, what is its use if the hook cannot catch fish?”

Kingfisher the Wise replies solemnly: – Straight hook was once used to catch... an emperor.”

In “The Weirdest Fishhook”; *The Kingfisher Story Collection* [1]

When pursuing a career in academia, scholars face challenges of academic competition and evaluation based on publication and citation metrics. The well-known saying “publish or perish” captures the publishing pressure which academics must bear to advance their careers. Researchers in low-resource nations and those in their early careers (ECRs) seem to feel the most pressure since they lack access to mentorship, resources, experience, and knowledge. Consequently, they usually encounter multiple setbacks, such as mental health issues and career dropouts. Thus, the SM3D community coaching portal is built to support social sciences and humanities researchers in conducting and publishing their studies on a global scale, especially Early Career Researchers (ECRs) and those in low-resource settings [2].

The SM3D portal was planned during its co-founders’ retreat in Pu Luong, Thanh Hoa, Vietnam, in late May and officially launched on June 21, 2022, with its first article [3]. Mindsponge thinking and Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics are the coaching program’s backbone theory and analytical tools [4,5]. At that time, we had some predictions about the community’s future direction but not its growth pace. Thus, it is worth recalling the development of the portal in the last year and how the BMF analytics/Mindsponge Theory (MT) have supported academics in constructing, performing, and finalizing their studies.

The report aims to list all BMF analytics/ MT users since their early development [4-6]. Not all people citing the BMF analytics/ MT are considered users. Only those who used BMF analytics/ MT substantively as a method in their studies are considered users (i.e., employed BMF analytics/ MT as the theoretical foundation, methodology, or reasoning framework for their findings). The records include authors that have employed the **bayesvl** R package [7], a fundamental component of BMF analytics, and the mindsponge mechanism (MM), the foundational conceptual framework for Mindsponge Theory [8,9]. Through the list, the AISDL team also hopes to help researchers interested in BMF analytics/MT reduce the time and effort for information seeking [10], enhance proactiveness [11], and facilitate knowledge exchange and community dialogue through transparency [12,13].

As of January 20, 2024, we recorded 168 documents (including articles, books, proceedings, and lectures) that have used Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics/Mindsponge Theory (MT) substantively. This number has increased by 31.25% since the previous record on July 9, 2023. The documents have been authored or co-authored by 330 researchers from 215 institutions in 38 countries, of which 67% come from developing/emerging countries. Among 330 users, 32 are registered members of the SM3D Portal.

No matter how rapidly the community is expanding, we have firmly adhered to our original philosophical principles set out in [10,13]. This helps walk us through the post-COVID-19 tumultuous period and the stagnation thereof.

As we enter the third year of operation, let’s look forward to making better and more meaningful achievements together, hoping new members will join our happy home.

Researchers with substantive BMF analytics/ MT applications in their studies

No.	Name	Affiliation	Country	Starting year	Publications	Remarks
1	Quan-Hoang Vuong	- Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University - A.I. for Social Data Lab (AISDL), Vuong & Associates	Vietnam	NA	[14-30]	AISDL Team
2	Viet-Phuong La	- Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University - A.I. for Social Data Lab (AISDL), Vuong & Associates	Vietnam	NA	[18,22,25,31]	AISDL Team
3	Minh-Hoang Nguyen	- Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University - A.I. for Social Data Lab (AISDL), Vuong & Associates	Vietnam	NA	[15-25,27,30,32-35]	AISDL Team
4	Nancy K Napier	- Boise State University	USA	2014	[36,37]	MM only/non-member
5	Vu Kim Hanh	- Centre for Business Studies and Assistance	Vietnam	2014	[36]	MM only
6	Nguyen Manh Cuong	- Vietnam Institute for Social Studies	Vietnam	2014	[36]	MM only
7	Tran Tri Dung	- DHVP Research	Vietnam	2014	[36]	MM only
8	Quang-Khiem Bui	- Hanoi College of Arts	Vietnam	2018	[38,39]	bayesvl only
9	Thu-Trang Vuong	- Sciences Po Paris	France	2018	[38-55]	Member
10	Manh-Tung Ho	- Vietnam Academy of Social Sciences, Institute of Philosophy - Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University - Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University	Vietnam, France	2018	[38,42,50,51,55-65]	Non-member

11	Hong-Kong To Nguyen	- Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University	Vietnam	2018	[38-40,42,60,66]	MM/ bayesvl only
12	Manh-Toan Ho	- Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University	Vietnam	2018	[38-40,43-49,56-58,61,66-76]	MM/ bayesvl only
13	Viet-Ha T. Nguyen	- Thanh Tay University	Vietnam	2018	[39]	bayesvl only
14	Tam Tri Le	- Graduate School of Asia Pacific Studies, Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University	Japan	2019	[16-22,24,27,31,77-79]	Member
15	Serik Meirmanov	- Graduate School of Asia Pacific Studies, Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University	Japan	2019	[55,78]	MM only
16	Hong-Ngoc Nguyen	- Ho Chi Minh City University of Fine Arts	Vietnam	2019	[38]	bayesvl only
17	Kien-Cuong P. Nghiem	- Vietnam-Germany Hospital	Vietnam	2019	[38,41]	bayesvl only
18	Anh-Vinh Le	- Vietnam National Institute of Educational Sciences	Vietnam	2019	[40]	bayesvl only
19	Duc-Lan Do	- Vietnam National Institute of Educational Sciences	Vietnam	2019	[40]	bayesvl only
20	Duc-Quang Pham	- Vietnam National Institute of Educational Sciences	Vietnam	2019	[40]	bayesvl only
21	Phuong-Hanh Hoang	- Vietnam National Institute of Educational Sciences	Vietnam	2019	[40,42]	bayesvl only
22	Thu-Huong Duong	- Vietnam National Institute of Educational Sciences	Vietnam	2019	[40]	bayesvl only
23	Hoai-Nam Nguyen	- ICT Department, Ministry of Education and Training	Vietnam	2019	[40]	bayesvl only
24	Trung Tran	- Vietnam Academy for Ethnic Minorities	Vietnam	2019	[41-43,57,71]	Member
25	Oana Bărbulescu	- Transilvania University of Braşov	Romania	2020	[80]	MM only
26	Alina Simona Tecău	- Transilvania University of Braşov	Romania	2020	[80]	MM only
27	Daniel Munteanu	- Transilvania University of Braşov	Romania	2020	[80]	MM only

28	Cristinel Petrișor Constantin	- Transilvania University of Brașov	Romania	2020	[80]	MM only
29	Huyen Thanh T. Nguyen	- Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University	Vietnam	2020	[43,44,49,66-68,70,72-75]	Non-member
30	Thanh-Hang Pham	- School of Business, RMIT Vietnam University	Vietnam	2020	[43,45-48,58,67]	MM/ bayesvl only
31	Quy Van Khuc	- VNU University of Economics and Business, Vietnam National University	Vietnam	2020	[43,47,54,68,81-90]	Member
32	Khanh-Linh Hoang	- Institute of Theoretical and Applied Research (ITAR), Duy Tan University	Vietnam	2020	[42]	bayesvl only
33	Thi-Hanh Vu	- School of Economics and International Business, Foreign Trade University	Vietnam	2020	[42,46,58]	bayesvl only
34	Peter Mantello	- Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University	Japan	2020	[56,59-61,63]	bayesvl only
35	Khanh-Linh P. Nguyen	- Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University	Vietnam	2020	[43]	bayesvl only
36	Anh-Phuong Luong	- School of Economics and International Business, Foreign Trade University	Vietnam	2020	[44]	bayesvl only
37	Thanh-Dung Nguyen	- School of Economics and International Business, Foreign Trade University	Vietnam	2020	[43,44]	bayesvl only
38	Thi-Linh Nguyen	- School of Economics and International Business, Foreign Trade University	Vietnam	2020	[43,44]	bayesvl only
39	Ha-My Vuong	- A.I. for Social Data Lab, Vuong & Associates	Vietnam	2020	[45,48,49]	bayesvl only
40	Hung-Hiep Pham	- Center for Research and Practice on Education, Phu Xuan University - EdLab Asia Educational Research and Development Centre	Vietnam	2020	[45,46,58]	bayesvl only
14	Anh-Duc Hoang	- School of Business and Management, RMIT Vietnam University - EdLab Asia Educational Research and Development Centre	Vietnam	2020	[45,58]	bayesvl only

41	Anh-Tuan Bui	- Faculty of Business Administration, Foreign Trade University	Vietnam	2021	[46,58]	bayesvl only
42	Hoang-Anh Ho	- Centre for Interdisciplinary Social Research, Phenikaa University	Vietnam	2021	[47]	bayesvl only
43	Sooksan Kantabutra	- College of Management, Mahidol University	Thailand	2021	[91,92]	MM only
44	Nuttasorn Ketprapakorn	- School of Business, University of the Thai Chamber of Commerce	Thailand	2021	[91]	MM only
45	Trang Nguyen	- School of Banking-Finance, National Economic University	Vietnam	2021	[82]	bayesvl only
46	Linh Pham	- Department of Economics, University of Central Oklahoma	USA	2021	[82]	bayesvl only
47	Dang-Trung Le	- Real-Time Analytics	Vietnam	2021	[82]	bayesvl only
48	Hong-Hai Ho	- Faculty of Business and Economics, Phenikaa University	Vietnam	2021	[82]	bayesvl only
49	Tien-Binh Truong	- Faculty of Business and Economics, Phenikaa University	Vietnam	2021	[82]	bayesvl only
50	Quoc-Khai Tran	- U Minh Ha National Park	Vietnam	2021	[82]	bayesvl only
51	Caroline Ärleskog	- School of Health and Welfare, Jönköping University - Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Gothenburg	Sweden	2021	[93]	MM only
52	Nicoline Vackerberg	- School of Health and Welfare, Jönköping University - Center for Learning and Innovation in Healthcare, Region Jönköping County	Sweden	2021	[93]	MM only
53	Ann-Christine Andersson	- School of Health and Welfare, Jönköping University - Faculty of Health and Society, Malmö University	Sweden	2021	[93]	MM only

54	Mahdi Rezapour	- Optim	Iran	2021	[94]	MM only
55	F. Richard Ferraro	- Department of Psychology, University of North Dakota	USA	2021	[94]	MM only
56	Sohayla El Fakahany	- School of Humanities and Social Sciences, The American University in Cairo	Egypt	2021	[95]	MM only
57	Quang-Loc Nguyen	- SP Jain School of Global Management	Australia	2022	[83,84,96-98]	Member
58	Thomas E. Jones	- Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University	Japan	2022	[99,100]	Member
59	Ruining Jin	- Civil, Commercial and Economic Law School, China University of Political Science and Law	China	2022	[2,53,54,77,79,84,96,97,101-106]	Member
60	Phuong-Tri Nguyen	- Securities Research and Training Center, State Security Commission	Vietnam	2022	[2,79,84,107]	Member
61	Truc-Le Nguyen	- VNU University of Economics and Business, Vietnam National University	Vietnam	2022	[81]	Member
62	Thuy Nguyen	- Vietkaplab	Vietnam	2022	[81,85,86,88]	Member
63	Hoang Khac Lich	- University of Economics and Business, Vietnam National University	Vietnam	2022	[81,90]	Member
64	Yalin Zhu	- Faculty of Education, Beijing Normal University - Nanhai Middle School of Nanshan Experimental Educational Group	China	2022	[108]	MM only
65	Linyuan Deng	- Faculty of Education, Beijing Normal University	China	2022	[108]	MM only
66	Kun Wan	- Faculty of Education, Beijing Normal University	China	2022	[108]	MM only
67	Thao Thi Phuong Nguyen	- Institute for Global Health Innovations, Duy Tan University	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
68	Tham Thi Nguyen	- Institute for Global Health Innovations, Duy Tan University	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only

69	Ha Ngoc Do	- Youth Research Institute, Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
70	Thao Bich Thi Vu	- Youth Research Institute, Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
71	Khanh Long Vu	- Youth Research Institute, Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
72	Hoang Minh Do	- Youth Research Institute, Ho Chi Minh Communist Youth Union	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
73	Nga Thu Thi Nguyen	- Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Hanoi Metropolitan University	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
74	Linh Phuong Doan	- Institute for Global Health Innovations, Duy Tan University	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
75	Giang Thu Vu	- Center of Excellence in Health Services and System Research, Nguyen Tat Thanh University	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
76	Hoa Thi Do	- Institute of Health Economics and Technology (iHEAT)	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
77	Son Hoang Nguyen	- Center of Excellence in Health Services and System Research, Nguyen Tat Thanh University	Vietnam	2022	[109]	MM only
78	Carl A. Latkin	- Bloomberg School of Public Health, Johns Hopkins University	USA	2022	[109]	MM only
79	Cyrus S. H. Ho	- Department of Psychological Medicine, National University Health System - Yong Loo Lin School of Medicine, National University of Singapore	Singapore	2022	[109]	MM only
80	Roger C. M. Ho	- Yong Loo Lin School of Medicine, National University of Singapore	Singapore	2022	[109]	MM only
81	Huimin Jia	- School of Public Health, Shanxi Medical University	China	2022	[110]	MM only
82	Xiaocheng Wang	- School of Public Health, Shanxi Medical University	China	2022	[110]	MM only
83	Jingmin Cheng	- School of Public Health, Shanxi Medical University	China	2022	[110]	MM only

84	Nader Ghotbi	- Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University	Japan	2022	[60]	bayesvl only
85	Tien-Chi Huang	- Department of Information Management, National Taichung University of Science and Technology	Taiwan	2022	[111]	MM only
86	Yi-Jin Wang	- Department of Information Management, National Taichung University of Science and Technology	Taiwan	2022	[111]	MM only
87	Hui-Min Lai	- Department of Business Administration, National Taichung University of Science and Technology	Taiwan	2022	[111]	MM only
88	Hailin Li	- College of Business Administration, Huaqiao University - Research Center for Applied Statistics and Big Data, Huaqiao University	China	2022	[112]	MM only
89	Hongqin Tang	- Research Center for Applied Statistics and Big Data, Huaqiao University	China	2022	[112]	MM only
90	Wenhao Zhou	- College of Business Administration, Huaqiao University	China	2022	[112]	MM only
91	Xiaoji Wan	- College of Business Administration, Huaqiao University	China	2022	[112]	MM only
92	Tao Zhang	- Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Macao Polytechnic University	China	2022	[113]	Member
93	Virginia Romano	- Eurac Research, Affiliated Institute of the University of Lübeck	Italy	2022	[114]	MM only
94	Mirko Ancillotti	- Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences, Uppsala University	Sweden	2022	[114]	MM only
95	Deborah Mascalonzi	- Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences, Uppsala University	Sweden	2022	[114]	MM only
96	Roberta Biasiotto	- Metabolic and Neural Sciences, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia	Italy	2022	[114]	MM only
97	Mohamed Allani	- Institut National Agronomique de Tunisie (INAT), Université de Carthage (UC)	Tunisia	2022	[115]	Non-member

98	Aymen Frija	- International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARADA)	Tunisia	2022	[115]	Non-member
99	Rabiaa Nemer	- Institut National Agronomique de Tunisie (INAT), Université de Carthage (UC)	Tunisia	2022	[115]	Non-member
100	Lars Ribbe	- Institute for Technology and Resources Management in the Tropics and Subtropics (ITT), TH Köln – University of Applied Sciences (THK)	Germany	2022	[115]	Non-member
101	Ali Sahli	- International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARADA)	Tunisia	2022	[115]	Non-member
102	Jie Wang	- College of Economics and Management, Nanjing Forestry University	China	2022	[116]	Non-member
103	Chang Liu	- College of Economics and Management, Nanjing Forestry University	China	2022	[116]	Non-member
104	Zhijian Cai	- College of Economics and Management, Nanjing Forestry University	China	2022	[116]	Non-member
105	Siyu Xu	- College of Economics and Management, Nanjing Agricultural University	China	2022	[117]	MM only
106	Yeye Zhao	- College of Economics and Management, Nanjing Agricultural University	China	2022	[117]	MM only
107	Noshaba Aziz	- College of Economics and Management, Nanjing Agricultural University	China	2022	[117]	MM only
108	Jun He	- College of Economics and Management, Nanjing Agricultural University	China	2022	[117]	MM only
109	Manish Kumar	- International Institute for Population Sciences	India	2022	[118]	MM only
110	Shobhit Srivastava	- International Institute for Population Sciences	India	2022	[118]	MM only
111	T. Muhammad	- International Institute for Population Sciences	India	2022	[118]	MM only
112	Priya Saravanakumar	- School of Nursing and Midwifery, University of Technology Sydney	Australia	2022	[118]	MM only
113	Nira Munichor	- The Graduate School of Business Administration, Bar-Ilan University	Israel	2022	[119]	Non-member
114	Alan D. J. Cooke	- Warrington College of Business Administration, University of Florida	USA	2022	[119]	Non-member

115	Zhenjing Pang	- School of Public Policy and Management, Tsinghua University	China	2022	[120]	MM only
116	Ce Zhao	- Beijing Language and Culture University	China	2022	[120]	MM only
117	Lan Xue	- School of Public Policy and Management, Tsinghua University	China	2022	[120]	MM only
118	Nanae Tanemura	- National Institutes of Biomedical Innovation, Health and Nutrition	Japan	2022	[121,122]	MM only
119	Tsuyoshi Chiba	- National Institutes of Biomedical Innovation, Health and Nutrition	Japan	2022	[121,122]	MM only
120	Yuting Cui	- Faculty of Education, Beijing Normal University	China	2022	[123]	MM only
121	Jon-Chao Hong	- Department of Industrial Education, National Taiwan Normal University - Institute for Research Excellence in Learning Sciences, National Taiwan Normal University	Taiwan	2022	[123]	MM only
122	Chi-Ruei Tsai	- International Master Program in STEM Education, National Pingtung University	Taiwan	2022	[123]	MM only
123	Jian-Hong Ye	- Faculty of Education, Beijing Normal University	Taiwan	2022	[123]	MM only
124	Masako Kakizaki	- Nagoya City University	Japan	2022	[122]	MM only
125	Takashi Kusumi	- Kyoto University	Japan	2022	[122]	MM only
126	Rie Onodera	- Osaka Metropolitan University	Japan	2022	[122]	MM only
127	Amanda Brockinton	- Faculty of Science and Technology, Bournemouth University	UK	2022	[124]	MM only
128	Sam Hirst	- Faculty of Social Sciences and Health, Durham University	UK	2022	[124]	MM only
129	Ruijie Wang	- Faculty of Science and Technology, Bournemouth University	UK	2022	[124]	MM only
130	John McAlaney	- Faculty of Science and Technology, Bournemouth University	UK	2022	[124]	MM only

131	Shelley Thompson	- Bournemouth Business School, Bournemouth University	UK	2022	[124]	MM only
132	Yulin Hswen	- Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, University of California San Francisco	USA	2022	[125]	MM only
133	Ulrich Nguemdjo	- CNRS, AMSE	France	2022	[125]	MM only
134	Elad Yom-Tov	- Microsoft Research Israel	France	2022	[125]	MM only
135	Gregory M Marcus	- Division of Cardiology, University of California San Francisco	France	2022	[125]	MM only
136	Bruno Ventelou	- CNRS, AMSE	France	2022	[125]	MM only
137	Shuangyu Zhao	- Vanke School of Public Health, Tsinghua University	China	2022	[126]	MM only
138	Yun Liang	- Vanke School of Public Health, Tsinghua University	China	2022	[126]	MM only
139	Jia Yi Hee	- Vanke School of Public Health, Tsinghua University	China	2022	[126]	MM only
140	Xinran Qi	- Department of Epidemiology, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health	USA	2022	[126]	MM only
141	Kun Tang	- Vanke School of Public Health, Tsinghua University	China	2022	[126]	MM only
142	Carolyn A. Stalgaitis	- Rescue Agency San Diego	USA	2022	[127]	MM only
143	Jeffrey W. Jordan	- Rescue Agency San Diego	USA	2022	[127]	MM only
144	Mayo Djakaria	- Rescue Agency San Diego	USA	2022	[127]	MM only
145	Daniel J. Saggese	- Virginia Foundation for Healthy Youth	USA	2022	[127]	MM only
146	Hannah Robbins Bruce	- Virginia Foundation for Healthy Youth	USA	2022	[127]	MM only
147	Yating Zhang	- Faculty of International Tourism and Management, City University of Macau	China	2022	[128]	MM only

148	Huawen Shen	- Faculty of International Tourism and Management, City University of Macau	China	2022	[128]	MM only
149	Jiajia Xu	- Faculty of International Tourism and Management, City University of Macau	China	2022	[128]	MM only
150	Stella Fang Qian	- Faculty of Business Administration, University of Macau	China	2022	[128]	MM only
151	Mai Trong Tri	- Endocrinology Department, People's Hospital 115	Vietnam	2022	[129]	MM only
152	Nguyen Thy Khue	- Ho Chi Minh City University of Medicine and Pharmacy	Vietnam	2022	[129]	MM only
153	Vo Tuan Khoa	- Endocrinology Department, People's Hospital 115	Vietnam	2022	[129]	MM only
154	Aya Goto	- Center for Integrated Science and Humanities, Fukushima Medical University	Japan	2022	[129]	MM only
155	Linli Jiang	- School of Economics and Management, Wuyi University	China	2022	[130]	MM only
156	Haoqin Huang	- School of Economics and Management, Wuyi University	China	2022	[130]	MM only
157	Surong He	- School of Economics and Management, Wuyi University	China	2022	[130]	MM only
158	Haiyang Huang	- School of Economics and Management, Wuyi University	China	2022	[130]	MM only
159	Yun Luo	- National Post-Doctoral Innovation (Jiangmen) Demonstration Center	China	2022	[130]	MM only
160	Marius Baranauskas	- Faculty of Biomedical Sciences, Panevėžys University of Applied Sciences	Lithuania	2022	[131]	MM only
161	Ingrida Kupčiūnaitė	- Faculty of Biomedical Sciences, Panevėžys University of Applied Sciences	Lithuania	2022	[131]	MM only
162	Rimantas Stukas	- Institute of Health Sciences of the Faculty of Medicine, Vilnius University	Lithuania	2022	[131]	MM only
163	Rongzhao Wang	- School of Psychology, Fujian Normal University	China	2022	[132]	MM only

164	Xuanxuan Lin	- School of Psychology, Fujian Normal University	China	2022	[132]	MM only
165	Zetong Ye	- School of Psychology, Fujian Normal University	China	2022	[132]	MM only
166	Hua Gao	- School of Psychology, Fujian Normal University	China	2022	[132]	MM only
167	Jianrong Liu	- School of Psychology, Fujian Normal University	China	2022	[132]	MM only
168	Yuan Ying Jin	- Department of Education, Sejong University	Korea	2022	[133]	MM only
169	Sungsik Ahn	- The Graduate School of Education, Keimyung University	Korea	2022	[133]	MM only
170	Sang Min Lee	- Department of Education, Korea University	Korea	2022	[133]	MM only
171	Yan Peng	- Business School, Huang Gang Normal University	China	2022	[134]	MM only
172	Kai Zeng	- School of Management, Zhejiang University of Technology	China	2022	[135]	MM only
173	Duanxu Wang	- School of Management, Zhejiang University	China	2022	[135]	MM only
174	Zhengwei Li	- School of Management, Zhejiang University of Technology	China	2022	[135]	MM only
175	Yujing Xu	- School of Management, Zhejiang University of Technology	China	2022	[135]	MM only
176	Xiaofen Zheng	- School of Management, Zhejiang University of Technology	China	2022	[135]	MM only
	Minh-Phuong Thi Duong	- Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Ton Duc Thang University	Vietnam	2023	[79]	Member
	Manh-Cuong Nguyen	- Berlin School of Business and Innovation	Germany	2023	[79]	Member
	Noah Mutai	- Berlin School of Business and Innovation	Germany	2023	[79]	Member
177	Thi-Phuong Nguyen	- Centre for Crop Systems Analysis, Wageningen University & Research	Netherlands	2023	[2,53,97,136]	Member
178	Giang Hoang	- Monash Business School, Monash University	Australia	2023	[2,53,104,107]	Member
179	Thao Dang	- Department of Gender, Sexuality, and Women's Studies, Western University of Ontario	Canada	2023	[85,86]	Member

180	Mai Tran	- Vietkap	Vietnam	2023	[85,86,88]	Member
181	Phu Pham	- Institute of Ecology and Biological Resources, Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology	Vietnam	2023	[85,86]	Member
182	Trung Tran	- School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Ulsan	Korea	2023	[85]	Member
183	Dang Trung Tuyen	- VNU University of Economics and Business, Vietnam National University	Vietnam	2023	[86]	Member
184	Luu Quoc Dat	- VNU University of Economics and Business, Vietnam National University	Vietnam	2023	[86]	Member
185	Hong-Son Nguyen	- Office of CPV Central Committee	Vietnam	2023	[54,136-138]	Member
186	Minh-Hieu Thi Nguyen	- School of Psychology, Massey University	New Zealand	2023	[96,97,104,136]	Member
187	Phuong-Loan Nguyen	- Spanish Department, Hanoi University	Vietnam	2023	[98,104,136,139]	Member
188	Minh-Khanh La	- School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Hanoi University of Science and Technology	Vietnam	2023	[101,102]	Member
189	Xiao Wang	- Suzhou Lunhua Education Group	China	2023	[103,105]	Member
190	Rameez Raja	- School of Sociology and Anthropology, Sun Yat-sen University	China	2023	[140]	Non-member
191	Jianfu Ma	- Pakistan Studies Centre, North Minzu University	China	2023	[140]	Non-member
192	Miwei Zhang	- PKUFH-Ningxia Women Children's Hospital	China	2023	[140]	Non-member
193	Xi Yuan Li	- School of Sociology and Anthropology, Sun Yat-sen University MIT	China	2023	[140]	Non-member
194	Nayef Shabbab Almutairi	- Al-lith College of Health Sciences, Umm Al-Qura University	Saudi Arabia	2023	[140]	Non-member
195	Aeshah Hamdan Almutairi	- Al-lith College of Health Sciences, Umm Al-Qura University	Saudi Arabia	2023	[140]	Non-member
196	Rongxiu Wu	- Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics, Harvard University	USA	2023	[141]	MM only

197	Khodran Alzahrani	- College of Food and Agriculture Sciences, King Saud University	Saudi Arabia	2023	[142]	Non-member
198	Mubashar Ali	- College of Food and Agriculture Sciences, King Saud University	Saudi Arabia	2023	[142]	Non-member
199	Muhammad Imran Azeem	- College of Food and Agriculture Sciences, King Saud University	Saudi Arabia	2023	[142]	Non-member
200	Bader Alhafi Alotaibi	- College of Food and Agriculture Sciences, King Saud University	Saudi Arabia	2023	[142]	Non-member
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203	Xuzhou Li	- Faculty of Education, Yunnan Normal University	China	2023	[143]	MM only
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205	Tingyu Ma	- School of Public Finance and Taxation, Zhongnan University of Economics and Law	China	2023	[144]	MM only
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209	Lluís Parcerisa	- Universitat de Barcelona	Spain	2023	[145]	Non-member
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216	Vincenzo Cestari	- Department of Psychology, Sapienza University	Italy	2023	[146]	Non-member
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219	Xiaoning Sun	- School of Medicine, Shanghai Jiao Tong University	China	2023	[148]	MM only
220	Jingyu Zhang	- CAS Key Laboratory of Behavioral Science, Institute of Psychology	China	2023	[141,148]	MM only
221	Xianghong Sun	- CAS Key Laboratory of Behavioral Science, Institute of Psychology	China	2023	[141,148]	MM only
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224	Yunzhou Cui	- School of Business, Qingdao University	China	2023	[149]	Non-member
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228	Mohit Kumar	- MIT Art, Design and Technology University	India	2023	[151]	Non-member
229	Ashwani Kumar	- SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Delhi-NCR Campus	India	2023	[151]	Non-member
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242	Brandon Bernal-Baldenebro	- Autonomous University of Baja California	Mexico	2023	[153]	Non-member
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	Wondwossen Yimam	- College of Medicine & Health Sciences, Wollo University	Ethiopia	2023	[163]	Non-member
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	Trung H. Nguyen	- Department of Environmental Science, Regrow Ag	USA	2023	[90]	Non-member
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	Mary Bresnahan	- Department of Communication, Michigan State University	USA	2024	[171]	Non-member
	Yuan Huang	- Research Center for Eco-Environmental Sciences, Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	2024	[172]	Non-member
	Yilei Hou	- School of Economics & Management, Beijing Forestry University	China	2024	[172]	Non-member
	Jie Ren	- School of Economics & Management, Beijing Forestry University	China	2024	[172]	Non-member
	Jie Yang	- School of Economics & Management, Beijing Forestry University	China	2024	[172]	Non-member
	Yali Wen	- School of Economics & Management, Beijing Forestry University	China	2024	[172]	Non-member
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